

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems / IPBES transformative change assessment (4.5)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address a range of constraints and challenges that arise within and between political, legal, technological, physical (e.g., infrastructure), economic/financial and other social systems and the functioning of ecosystems and how these challenges could be overcome. The chapter provides evidence on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems as being one of the challenges impeding transformative change. In this context, a review of literature focused on this challenge was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

The evidence for Section 4.2.5 was gathered within a conceptual research methodology using a systematic review through five processes to examine the challenges regarding limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems. The processes comprised the identification of the scope of the study, the selection of an appropriate database, data collection, data analysis and reporting results.

Process 1: Identifying the scope of the study

The review used an inductive perspective because it was not clear what types of challenges are important for transformative change and how they can be categorized. Since the beginning of designing and writing chapter 4, the team members of the chapter in regular virtual meetings and their first in-person meeting suggested some initial concepts for challenges of transformative change, including challenges of section 5. This led to defining some terms to be used for initial search by google scholar and Scopus, emerging new concepts inductively and writing the first order draft by December 2022. The results of the first external review and the second author meeting in Costa Rica and following virtual meetings suggested some other concepts, which changed the review procedure. Through expert knowledge, the section identified main challenges regarding the generation and access to clean or green or sustainable technologies, coordination within and between knowledge and innovation systems, Indigenous and local knowledge and its relationship with scientific knowledge. The review used an inductive perspective.

Authors searched for relevant literature using the SCOPUS database and Google Scholar and applied keyword filtering to refine the results. The SCOPUS database has been recommended by many researchers because it has more extensive sources than others. The data collection and search were initiated by Google Scholar, followed by searching Scopus database and developed by Google Scholar search (particularly for grey literature regarding the challenges of emergent technologies). In addition to using the above-mentioned keywords, authors used other emerging concepts for search such as challenges of Indigenous and local knowledge, planned obsolescence and premature ageing of technologies, transfer of or access to knowledge and emergent technologies (such as gene-editing technologies). The systematic review employed two data analysis techniques of bibliographic and thematic analyses. The bibliographic analysis used a descriptive perspective and identified to examine the documents by publication year, main subjects, type of documents, sources of documents, country of the document authors and affiliation of authors the research.

Details search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** systematic review with keyword filtering
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "knowledge systems" OR "knowledge and innovation systems" OR "clean technolog*" OR "clean innovation*" OR "green technolog*" OR "green innovation*" OR "sustainable innovation" OR "sustainable technological innovation*" OR "open innovation*" ) AND
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TITLE-ABS-KEY ("barrier*" OR "obstacle" OR "challenge*" OR "limited access" OR "limited availability" OR "lack of access" OR "unavailability") AND

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("sustainability" OR "sustainable development" OR "biodiversity Governance" OR "transformation" OR "transformative Change" OR "biodiversity restoration" OR "biodiversity management")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

- **Search languages:** English. Some documents in other languages, which had the English title or abstract without English full texts, e.g., Spanish, Chinese, French and Persian were also included in the search.
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS
- **Sample extracted:** 1634 documents (English title or abstract), including 1591 documents in full English text, based on a reading of titles, abstracts and keywords (**A**).
- **Treatment applied:** the first search was complemented by a Google Scholar search using the same keywords. See search 2.

Figure 1. Number of documents published between 1980 and 2023 (n=161)

Figure 2. Top 23 (publishing at least two articles per source) out of 125 sources that published documents between 1980 and 2023 (n=161)

Figure 3. Top 30 out of 67 countries contributed in publication between 1980 and 2023¹ (n=134)

¹ From Scopus database. The data was not available for the 27 documents searched in Google Scholar.

Figure 4. Top 34 out of 160 institutions worldwide published between 1980 and 2023 (n=134)

Figure 5. Number of results by subjects published between 1980 and 2023 (n=161)

Figure 6. Number of results by publication type between 1980 and 2023 (n=161). The three documents without labels consisted of one "Letter", one "Editorial" and one thesis.

Figure 7. Top 14 out of 90 funding sponsors of articles published between 1980 and 2023 (n=134, from Scopus database)

Details search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** thematic analysis with keyword filtering
- **Search terms:**

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( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "knowledge systems" OR "knowledge and innovation systems" OR "clean technolog*" OR "clean innovation*" OR "green technolog*" OR "green innovation*" OR "sustainable innovation" OR "sustainable technological innovation*" OR "open innovation*" ) AND
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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "barrier*" OR "obstacle" OR "challenge*" OR "limited access" OR "limited availability" OR "lack of access" OR "unavailability" ) AND
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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "sustainability" OR "sustainable development" OR "biodiversity Governance" OR "transformation" OR "transformative Change" OR "biodiversity restoration" OR
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"biodiversity management")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE ,
"English"))

- **Search languages:** English. Some documents in other languages, which had the English title or abstract without English full texts, e.g., Spanish, Chinese, French and Persian were also included in the search.
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Sample extracted:** 357 documents, based on a full text review **(B)**.
- **Treatment applied:** In addition to using the above-mentioned keywords, authors used other emerging concepts for search such as challenges of Indigenous and local knowledge, planned obsolescence and premature ageing of technologies, transfer of or access to knowledge, and emergent technologies (such as gene-editing technologies). The full text of documents also introduced new references which were reviewed to enhance the literature review. The results of google scholar search revealed over 544 documents, of which 200 were the same as those searched by Scopus database, but 344 documents were specifically identified by Google Scholar. The total documents searched by the two methods consisted of 1935.
- The review through screening the title, abstract and key Words of the documents and removing duplicated and grey literature identified 357 relevant documents for assessment and excluding 1578 documents. The final screening and reviewing the full text of the selected documents through thematic analysis identified that 161 documents are the most relevant for review. The review showed 357 documents are relevant for the assessment **(B)**. The final screening identified 161 documents **(C)**.

Overall treatment applied:

Thematic analysis was the second technique authors used to analyse the content of 161 documents. This technique is a way of analysing qualitative data that involves going through a data set and searching for patterns to create themes. It can use an inductive or deductive approach. Authors employed an inductive approach in this review. The inductive thematic analysis means finding meaning and themes from data without any preconceptions or any anticipated outcomes. The thematic analysis was used to extract codes or concepts and construct categories and themes. A code refers to a label assigned to a piece of data to indicate and summarise key concepts within a data set, while a theme denotes a pattern within the data. The data was analysed in six steps:

- a) Familiarising with the data before coding: reviewing the title, abstract and keywords and the main parts of each document to observe any meanings and patterns across the data set and take notes about them
- b) Open coding and creating the initial codes: this stage refers to identifying, extracting and creating concepts or initial codes and constructing initial categories to represent the patterns and meanings in the data. We read through the documents several times, applied appropriate codes from concepts and made a list of codes (a <http://codebook>) to record and follow the codes. The open coding used three procedures of identifying and extracting concepts, word by word, sentence by sentence and paragraph by paragraph. This helped with two types of concepts, In vivo concepts (direct concepts or codes extracted from the text) and constructed codes from several concepts with similar meaning.
- c) Categorising or collating codes: this means clustering codes to group all excerpts related to a particular code. We called these groups of codes as initial categories or sub-themes.

- d) Axial coding or grouping initial categories (grouped codes) into themes: This step refers to clustering of selective codes through sorting the initial categories or grouped codes into potential themes (principal or core categories), which represent trends and patterns in the data. Our review finally identified six themes.
- e) Reviewing, revising and finalising themes: we reviewed and revised the themes to represent the challenge of knowledge, technology and innovation systems from a comprehensive perspective. We merged some similar sub-themes and themes and finally decided to construct four distinct themes and use the supportive data from the documents to formulate the themes into a narrative.
- f) Writing the report

Based on the thematic analysis, the report was prepared in four main themes:

1. Generation and access to clean technology (N=50)
2. Ineffective coordination within and between knowledge & innovation systems (N=52)
3. Limited knowledge transfer and access to sustainable knowledge & innovation (N=36)
4. Emergent technologies (N=39)

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_4.5_11-2023_(A)	CSV	20 KB	List of references from the SCOPUS search
B	2_IPBES_TCA_4.5_11-2023_(B)	PDF	350 KB	List of references from the Google Scholar Search
C	3_IPBES_TCA_4.5_11-2023_(C)	PDF	283 KB	Final list of references included in Section 4.2.5.